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Promoting Positive Wellbeing of Teachers in The School Climate

Hale Erden ¹

Abstract: Teachers usually feel unprepared for the behaviours students bring to the school, which affect their wellbeing and teaching management. This promotes ways for the staff of the school and the policymakers to solve challenges to the teaching and learning process. Investigating ways to promote teachers' positive wellbeing in the school climate is the aim of the present research. Using survey methodology, the participants were teachers, school managers, and educational policymakers. Educational policymakers include the Minister of National Education, the Undersecretary of the Minister of Education, the Director of the General Secondary Education Department, and Members of the Education Union Board of Directors. Data were collected through surveys, observations, and audio recording transcripts of interviews. The identified wellbeing of teachers can be used to support teachers and students in creating a positive school climate. Findings revealed that there are several strategies that schools and policymakers can use to support teachers in promoting wellbeing and creating a positive school climate. Teachers' wellbeing is promoted through managing behaviours and teaching. It is concluded that behaviours that promote teachers' wellbeing are promoted through developing effective action, developing social skills, developing personal skills, and producing a safe and predictable school climate. In addition to this, teachers' wellbeing and teaching management are promoted through effective content and context and prompting leadership skills and qualities. As a result, policymakers are strongly urged to take a holistic approach to promote positive wellbeing and create a positive school climate. Implications provide teachers with opportunities to develop themselves professionally, to encourage collaboration and support, to use positive reinforcement strategies, to establish clear expectations and rules, to foster student engagement, to involve students' in decision-making processes, to give students a sense of ownership, and to adopt inclusive practises.

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Introduction

Education systems value teachers' wellbeing. Positive school climate and teachers' positive wellbeing influence each other. Teachers' behaviour management and teaching management skills contribute to their wellbeing. Researchers such as Tov and Diener (2009) and Ryan and Deci (2011) claim the universal definitions approved for the term wellbeing in the literature, named as satisfaction of life and flourishing of life. Ryan and Deci (2011) described the term wellbeing as something that promotes openness, is engaged, and has healthy functioning. This involves a global assessment of well-being across different domains of an individual's life.

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Wellbeing at work relates to a person's evaluating the work environment positively and considering the work place to be functioning (Tov & Diener, 2009). Regarding teachers, Diener (2009) claims that it is accepted as the wellbeing of teachers. Teachers' stress and teachers' burnout have been constructed based on teachers' work environment wellbeing (Pakarinen et al., 2010). It is important to understand wellbeing in different domains, including the domain of work, in order to fully understand an individual's overall wellbeing and identify ways to support it (Van Horn, Taris, Schaufeli, and Schreurs, 2004). It is important to study teachers' wellbeing from a positive perspective rather than just focusing on teacher stress and teacher burnout (Spilt, Koomen, & Thijs, 2011), in order to fully understand the factors that contribute to teachers' wellbeing and to identify ways to support it (Pakarinen and colleagues, 2010).

By looking at teachers' wellbeing from a positive perspective, it is possible to avoid the shortcoming and identify the factors that contribute to teachers' wellbeing rather than just focusing on the negative aspects of the profession (Duckworth et al., 2009). This can be helpful in developing strategies to support teachers' wellbeing and improve the overall teaching profession (Huppert & So, 2013).

Research on teachers' wellbeing is still relatively new, but it is a growing area of study, with more studies beginning to emerge that focus on teachers' wellbeing directly. (Aelterman, Engels, Van Petegem & Verhaeghe, 2007; Konu, Viitanen & Lintonen, 2010, Positive Schools Workshop Report, 2022; Gür & Eser, 2022; Positive Schools Workshop Report, 2023; Gür & 2023). It is important to continue to advance this line of inquiry in order to better understand the factors that impact teachers' wellbeing and identify ways to support it.

There are several factors that can impact teachers' wellbeing. Work stress, which refers to stress related to workload and job demands, is a common factor that can impact teachers' wellbeing. Organizational-level stress, which refers to stress related to school-level issues such as policies, procedures, and leadership, can also impact teachers' wellbeing. Student-related stress, which refers to stress related to student behaviour and the challenges of working with diverse groups of students, can also be a significant factor in teachers' wellbeing (Clunies-Ross, Little, Kienhuis, 2008; Collie et. al., 2012; Klassen & Chiu, 2011).

Emerging research suggests that these factors are relevant for teachers' wellbeing, and it is important to consider the impact of these factors on teachers' wellbeing in order to develop strategies to support and improve it (Aelterman et. al., 2007; Konu et. al., 2010). Studies regarding teachers' wellbeing have promoted new concepts and frameworks. Positive-emotions, satisfaction of job and job engagement related positive establishments and stress, strain, negative emotions, emotional exhaustion related negative establishments provide increases (Collie, et. al., 2015). Definition of teachers' wellbeing include cognitive conditions, emotional conditions, health conditions and social conditions in relation to teachers' professional (Viac and Fraser, 2020, p.18). Wellbeing of teachers and their satisfaction on their profession has been operationalised (Parker and Martin, 2009). Such kind of definitions cover teachers' wellbeing on wellbeing on the workplace (Parker, et. al., 2012), wellbeing on profession (Klusmann et. al., 2008), and wellbeing on claims regarding resources (Granziera, et. al., 2020). Wellbeing of teachers is closely related to wellbeing on subjects (Chan, 2010, 2013) and wellbeing on socio-ecological frameworks (McCallum, 2020). In addition to this, teachers' mental and physical health, engagement on profession, desire to leave a school have also closely related to teachers' wellbeing (Claeys, 2011; Kellr, Frenzel, et. al., 2014, O'Reilly, 2014). Teachers' wellbeing and teachers' effective teaching styles as well as choosing which teaching behaviour to apply, having affirmative emotions to connect, promoting enthusiasm and motivation in the class and developing the school effectiveness through contextually and individually have positively impact each other (Bajorek, et. al., 2014; Caprara, et. al., 2006.; Collie et. al., 2012; Fouche, et. al., 2017; Nazari and Alizadeh Oghyanous,

2021; Viac and Fraser, 2020).

Collaboration of teachers, degree of quality on relationship between student and teachers as well as teachers' autonomy on their profession have been found to be the contextual factors affecting school climate (Aloe et. al., 2014; Collie and Martin, 2017; Klassen et. al., 2012; Spilt et. al., 2011; Weiland, 2021). School climate has been defined as the context where teachers both work and teach using psychosocial factors (Johnson et. al., 2007, p. 111). School climate has been identified five dimensions which are listed as affiliation (feel of belonging to the school); innovativeness (feel of adaptation to recent methods and development); participating decision making process (autonomy and participation level of teachers to the decisions made in schools); adequate sources (feel of obtaining effective educational sources); support by the learners (quality level of teacher-student relationship) (Johnson, et al., 2007).

The relationship between teachers' wellbeing and school climate is complex and dynamic. The relationship can be influenced by a variety of factors, including behaviour management and teaching management. The well-being of teachers has been positively affected by workplace conditions and individual teacher behaviour. The aim of the current study is to identify how to promote the positive wellbeing skills of teachers in the school climate. By analysing interviews with participants, it is possible to gain insights into the professional work of the participants and the ways in which they cooperate in order to support the wellbeing of teachers. This can provide valuable knowledge about the school climate as a professional arena and the specific role that teachers play within it. Understanding these dynamics can help inform strategies for promoting teachers' wellbeing and improving the effectiveness of professional cooperation in the school climate.

Teachers' wellbeing is a complex and multifaceted concept that is closely related to various factors, including their mental and physical health, job satisfaction, engagement with their profession, and the school climate in which they work. Research has shown that teachers' wellbeing is closely related to their ability to effectively teach and engage with their students and that it is influenced by both individual teacher behaviours and contextual factors such as the school climate and the resources and support available to teachers.

Promoting the wellbeing of teachers is important for the overall functioning and effectiveness of the education system, as teachers who are stressed, burned out, or otherwise not well struggle to effectively teach and support their students. Strategies that may be helpful in promoting the wellbeing of teachers in the school climate include providing support for teachers' physical and mental health, promoting a positive and supportive school climate, and empowering teachers to have autonomy and decision-making power in their work. It is also important for policymakers and school leaders to consider the impact of broader social and ecological factors on teachers' wellbeing and to take a holistic approach to supporting teachers in the school climate.

Wellbeing among teachers has been linked to effective teaching and students' motivation for learning. Assessing teachers' work-related experiences and investigating how these impact their wellbeing can provide valuable insights into the factors that contribute to teachers' wellbeing and help identify ways to support it (Collie, Shapka, and Perry, 2012; Duckworth, Quinn, and Seligman, 2009). This approach, which focuses on understanding the core aspects of teachers' work that impact teachers' wellbeing, is a practically oriented approach as it helps to identify specific aspects of teachers' work that can be targeted for improvement (Duckworth et al., 2009). By understanding the factors that impact teachers' wellbeing and developing strategies to support it, it is possible to improve the overall teaching profession and create better outcomes for both teachers and students (Pakarinen et al., 2010).

Method

Context and Participants

The data reported stems from a broader study about teachers' wellbeing in the school climate across their teaching careers. Forty teachers and eighteen school managers volunteered to take part in the interviews. Throughout the study, the data were collected through interviews using self-completion surveys by the teachers and school managers, which were conducted between January and February 2021. The intention was to collect data from the teachers and the school managers regarding promoting teachers' wellbeing in the school climate. Self-completion surveys are used, aiming at providing greater anonymity for the participants since the absence of an interviewer ensures anonymity. The topic of the research is sensitive and personal; therefore, a self-completion survey is used to increase the reliability of the responses. Furthermore, a self-completion survey is used, aiming at reducing the bias and error caused by the interviewers' characteristics and the variability in their skills. In addition to self-completion surveys by teachers and school managers, teachers from pre-primary, primary, secondary, and high schools were observed in their classroom settings and school settings five times between March and June 2021. Each time, checklists were completed by the observer. Additionally, the interviews took place face-to-face with educational policymakers. Educational policy makers included the Minister of National Education, the Undersecretary of the Minister of Education, the Director of the General Secondary Education Department, and Members of the Education Union Board of Directors.

Research Tools and Procedures

This study used a combination of self-completion surveys, observations, and face-to-face interviews to collect data on promoting teachers' wellbeing in the school climate. The self-completion surveys were used to provide anonymity for the participants and to reduce bias and error caused by the interviewer's characteristics and skills. The observations were conducted in the classroom and school settings, with checklists completed by the researcher. Additionally, face-to-face interviews were conducted with educational policymakers. The study recruited forty teachers and eighteen school managers as participants, and data collection took place between January and February 2021 for the self-completion surveys and March and June 2021 for the observations.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations were taken into account before collecting data for the study. Both the Participant Information Form and the Consent Form were created. The Participant Information Form provided detailed information on the research, detailed information on the teachers' involvement, and detailed information on any potential risks or benefits. Additionally, the researcher ensured the storage of data securely, confidentially, and anonymously by removing identifying markers (like names of participants and schools, as well as venue, etc.) from the transcript and by destroying the original recording after transcription was completed.

Data Analysis

The survey protocol and observation protocol for the teachers had 'teachers' learning' and 'teaching experiences-based questions, present and previous motivational drives and attitudes towards teachers' choice of career, ecologies, identities as well as meaning, mental as well as physical wellbeing-based questions, and included 'their perspectives on how to promote the positive wellbeing of present and next generation teachers'. Similarly, the survey protocol for the school managers covered questions about the school managers' perspectives towards teachers' learning and teaching experiences, present and previous motivations and attitudes towards their choice of career, ecologies, identities as well as meaning, mental as well as physical wellbeing, and their perspectives on how to promote the positive wellbeing of present and next generation

teachers.

The semi-structured interview protocol for the educational planners included questions about the teachers, the school managers and the education system in terms of teachers' learning and teaching experiences, the present and previous motivational drives and attitudes toward teachers' choice of career, ecologies, identities as well as meaning, mental as well as physical wellbeing, and educational planners' perspectives on how to promote positive wellbeing of current and future teachers.

An approach, named the inductive analysis, as the part of the practices of the Grounded Theory was used for analysing the data. Ethical approval was obtained and measures were taken to ensure the anonymity and confidentiality of the participants.

The data analysis process for this study consisted of several stages and methods. Initially, the data were coded and repeatedly re-coded through using both the emergent as well as the sub-categories. The exploratory phase revealed that wellbeing of the participants was associated with processes involving multiple and continuously changing practices. The second stage involved describing the numerous contents for the wellbeing-system of each participant and evaluating how the participants' interact as well as how data were dynamic and stable. Finally, findings of the data were presented as individual vignettes to manage a comprehensive explanation for the wellbeing of the participants and avoid oversimplification of their personal life stories.

Results

It is important for teachers to have positive wellbeing in order to effectively manage their own wellbeing and the wellbeing of their students in the school climate. The findings of the current study reveal that there are strategies to promote the wellbeing of teachers in the school climate which are shown in Table 1 below:

Table 1: Strategies to Promote Wellbeing of Teachers in the School Climate

Identified Strategies	Specific Strategies	Useful Strategies
1. Identified strategies on behaviour management		
1a. Developing effective action This may involve providing teachers within the resources and support they need to manage their own wellbeing and the wellbeing of their students in the school climate. This could involve things like access to mental health resources, training on how to manage stress, and time for self-care.	1ai. Empowering School/Class Rules and Positive Behaviour	--Use Greetings (Say Hello/Goodbye/Thank you/Please/Excuse me) -Be in time -Use Students' Names
	1aii. Diminishing Negative Behaviour	-Bullying and Harassment -Swearing -Interrupting -Yelling out -Embarrassing others
	1aiii. Embossing Uniform	-Discipline -Classroom Management -Focus on equality between rich and poor
1b. Developing social skills Teachers who have strong social skills are better able to form positive relationships with their students, which can help to promote a positive school climate. This may involve providing training on how to effectively communicate and interact with students.	1bi. Raising	-Developing Self-Esteem, -Developing Valuable Values, -Developing Good Manners -Developing Skills
	1bii. Managing	-Manage/supervise effectively to reduce conflict -Communicate effectively with others -Work cooperatively in groups and with colleagues -Giving Effective Decisions in Challenging times and events -Manage to avoid anti-sociality
1c. Developing personal skills Teachers who have strong social skills are better able to form positive relationships	1ci. Caring	-Care for others and care for the school environment -Caring for wildlife

with their students, which can help to promote a positive school climate. This may involve providing training on how to effectively communicate and interact with students.	1cii. Valuing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Smile and Be Polite towards others -Look at students when talking -Listen -Accept Differences -Respect opinions of others -Give Compliments -Courtesy -Responsibility (Rights and Responsibilities) -Respect yourself and Respect others -Value the environment -Seek/Search for Knowledge -Achieve your potential -Contribute positively to society
1d. Producing a safe and predictable school climate A safe and predictable school climate can help to promote the wellbeing of teachers and students. This may involve implementing clear rules and consequences, providing support for students who are struggling, and promoting a culture of respect and inclusion.	1di. Promoting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Transferring cultural heritage -Using environmentally-friendly materials -Reducing-Reusing-Recycling
2. Identified strategies on teaching management	1dii. Sustaining	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Contributing effectively to clean-up -Conserving and renewing resources
2a. Teaching effective content and context Teachers who are able to effectively teach the material they are responsible for can help to promote a positive school climate. This may involve providing training on how to effectively plan and deliver lessons, as well as how to support students who are struggling	2ai. Developing Content for school instruction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Writing clear and measurable Content goals -Producing sustainable Sources -Promoting Structure -Developing Quantity -Performing student friendly Activities
2b. Promoting leadership skills and qualities Teachers who are able to demonstrate strong leadership skills and qualities, such as adaptability and decision-making, can help to promote a positive school climate. This may involve providing training on how to develop these skills and qualities.	2aai. Promoting context for school instruction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Supporting effective teaching and learning
	2bi. Leading and Managing Colleagues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Planning, Arranging and Running the Curriculum -Working alongside colleagues in classrooms -Listening to Colleagues -Keeping colleagues up to date -Keeping parents and community updated
	2bii. Efficient and effective deployment of colleagues and resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Selecting and ordering materials and equipment -Organizing storage and making sure resources are accessible -Demonstrating use of equipment -Finding out about new resources -Monitoring the budget -Auditing resources - Finding alternative ways of using the environment -Assessing risks with equipment and activities
	2biii. Developing plans to prepare yourself as a curriculum leader	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Increasing leadership qualities and strategies for instructional leadership -Using learner centered instruction -Monitoring -Applying basic instructor practices

Findings

Developing social and personal skills is important for teachers in order to create a positive and supportive learning environment for their students (Rüütman et al., 2021). Focusing on strategies for developing social skills involves specific strategies such as raising self-esteem, developing valuable values, developing good manners, and developing skills (Social and Emotional Skills: Wellbeing, Connectedness, and Success, n.d.; Davies and Cooper, 2014). Additionally, it is important for teachers to be able to manage effectively in order to reduce conflict and promote positive interactions with others. This involves being able to communicate effectively

with others, work cooperatively in groups and with colleagues, make effective decisions in challenging times and events, and avoid behaving in an anti-social manner.

Similarly, focusing on strategies for developing personal skills involves specific strategies such as caring for others and the school environment, being polite and smiling at others, and valuing diversity and the opinions of others. It is also important for teachers to be responsible, respectful, and seek knowledge in order to achieve their full potential and contribute positively to society. Valuing the environment and practising sustainability are also vital for promoting a positive and supportive learning environment (Parsonson, 2012). Furthermore, creating a safe and predictable environment is good for promoting a positive and supportive learning environment for students (Dreer, 2022; Mercer and Dörnyei, 2020). Specific strategies for producing a safe and predictable environment involve promoting and sustaining specific practises, such as transferring cultural heritage, using environmentally friendly materials, reducing, reusing, and recycling, and contributing effectively to clean-up and resource conservation efforts (Amerstorfer and Frein von Münster-Kistner, 2021).

Teaching effective content and context is also important for promoting a positive and supportive learning environment (Creating Effective Teaching and Learning Environments, 2009; Sithole, 2017). Specific strategies for developing content for school instruction involve writing clear and measurable content goals, using sustainable sources, promoting structure, and using student-friendly activities. Promoting leadership skills and qualities has important implications for teachers in order to effectively lead and manage their colleagues and resources, establish a learning culture, and promote effective teaching and learning. Specific skills for promoting leadership include leading and managing colleagues, developing plans as a curriculum leader, and promoting distributed instructional leadership (Day and Sammons, 2016).

Leading and managing colleagues is an important aspect of promoting leadership skills and qualities in teachers (Carswell, 2021; Pont, et al., 2008). Specific strategies for leading and managing colleagues include planning and running the curriculum, working alongside colleagues in classrooms, listening to colleagues, keeping colleagues up-to-date, and keeping parents and communities updated.

Deploying efficient and effective colleagues and resources is also important for promoting leadership skills and qualities (Osborne and Hammoud, 2017). Specific strategies for deploying efficient and effective colleagues and resources include selecting and ordering materials and equipment, organising storage and making resources accessible, demonstrating the use of equipment, finding new and alternative resources, monitoring the budget, auditing resources, finding alternative ways of using the environment, and assessing risks with equipment and activities.

Developing plans as a curriculum leader is another aspect of promoting leadership skills and qualities (High Impact Teaching Strategies: Excellence in Teaching and Learning, 2020, revised edition). Specific strategies for developing plans as a curriculum leader include increasing leadership qualities and strategies for instructional leadership, using learner-centred instruction, and monitoring and applying basic instructor practises. Similarly, promoting distributed instructional leadership for effective teaching and learning is another important aspect of promoting leadership skills and qualities. Specific strategies for promoting distributed instructional leadership include being an instructor as part of the teaching team, promoting teacher leadership, and motivating and stimulating instructors (Gray, Wilcox, and Nordstokke, 2017).

Establishing a learning culture is an aspect of promoting leadership skills and qualities. Specific strategies for establishing a learning culture include being responsible for creating a learning culture in a school, leading the school as a context and workplace, improving sociability, and empowering solidarity (Creating Learning Cultures: Assessing the Evidence, 2020).

Teaching learning components is another important aspect of promoting leadership skills and qualities. Specific strategies for teaching learning components include applying policies, using current and effective technology, constructing sustainable processes, leading human resources, and developing skills and responsibilities. (Didham and Ofei-Manu, 2018).

As a result, promoting positive wellbeing among teachers in the school climate requires teachers to have a range of social and personal skills in order to create a positive and inclusive classroom environment. Additionally, creating a safe and predictable environment, teaching effective content and context, and promoting leadership skills and qualities are all important aspects of being an effective teacher. It is also important for teachers to be able to lead and manage their colleagues and resources effectively and to develop plans as a curriculum leader in order to support student learning. Promoting positive wellbeing among teachers is also crucial and can be achieved through self-care, a culture of support, professional development opportunities, and work-life balance. Overall, it is clear that being a successful teacher requires a range of skills and qualities, and that promoting positive wellbeing is an important part of the process.

Conclusions and Recommendations

It appears that the findings provided a set of strategies for promoting the positive wellbeing of teachers in the school climate. These strategies focus on several key areas, including developing effective actions, developing social skills, developing personal skills, producing a safe and predictable environment, teaching effective content and context, and promoting leadership skills and qualities. Some specific strategies that were mentioned include using greetings and other good manners, reducing negative behaviour such as bullying and harassment, promoting cultural heritage and environmentally friendly materials, organising resources and equipment, using learner-centred instruction, establishing a learning culture, and developing policies and technology to support effective teaching and learning. It is important for schools to consider these strategies and find ways to support teachers in developing and maintaining positive wellbeing in order to create a positive and supportive school climate.

To conclude, educators serving in schools and policymakers can use the following strategies to support teachers in promoting positive wellbeing and creating a positive school climate:

1. Professional development: Providing ongoing professional development opportunities for teachers can help them learn new strategies and techniques for promoting positive wellbeing and managing the classroom effectively.
2. Collaboration and support: Encouraging collaboration and support among teachers can help them share ideas and resources and build a sense of community within the school.
3. Positive reinforcement: Using positive reinforcement strategies, such as praising students for their positive behaviours and efforts, can help create a positive school climate.
4. Clear expectations and rules: Establishing clear expectations and rules for behaviour can help create a sense of structure and predictability in the classroom, which can support positive wellbeing and academic success.
5. Student engagement: Fostering student engagement through activities and projects that are meaningful and relevant to students can help create a positive school climate and promote positive wellbeing.
6. Student voice: Involving students in decision-making and giving them a sense of ownership and agency can help create a positive school climate and promote positive wellbeing.
7. Inclusive practises: Adopting inclusive practises, such as promoting diversity and equity, can help create a positive school climate for all students.

As a result, it is important for teachers, school managers, and policymakers to take a holistic approach to promoting positive wellbeing and creating a positive school climate and to consider the various factors that can impact student wellbeing and academic success. Teacher wellbeing is a complex and multifaceted concept that has been approached from a variety of angles in research. While some studies have focused on one-dimensional measures such as job satisfaction, others have adopted multi-dimensional frameworks or concepts from positive psychology or socio-ecological models.

Pedagogical Implications and Further Research

Regarding the strategies for promoting positive wellbeing among teachers in the school climate, it is important for teachers to focus on developing effective actions in order to create a positive and productive learning environment for their students. This can involve empowering school and class rules and promoting positive behaviour as well as diminishing negative behaviour. Specific strategies such as greetings, being punctual, and using students' names can be useful in achieving this goal. Additionally, it is important for teachers to focus on specific strategies such as avoiding bullying and harassment, avoiding swearing, avoiding interrupting, and avoiding embarrassing others in order to create a safe and respectful environment for all students. Enforcing a uniform code can also be a useful strategy for promoting discipline and managing the classroom effectively. Finally, it is important for teachers to focus on equality and fairness in order to create a positive school climate for all students. Overall, it is important for school managers and policymakers to support teachers in developing and maintaining positive wellbeing in order to promote a positive and supportive school climate.

Teachers' mental and physical health, job engagement, and student wellbeing, motivation, and achievement have been influenced by both individual factors such as teaching style and behaviour as well as contextual factors such as the school climate and the support and resources available to teachers. Further research is needed to better understand the complex interplay between various factors impacting the wellbeing of teachers. This is crucial given that the wellbeing of teachers has a meaningful impact on the learning of students and on overall school effectiveness.

One further area of research can focus on the effectiveness of interventions aimed at improving aspects of teachers' work, diminishing work load, and promoting the wellbeing of teachers. Such interventions can be evaluated in terms of their impact on the wellbeing of teachers, their job satisfaction, and their overall productivity.

Another area of research can be on assessing the wellbeing of teachers at both individual and school levels, as it is important to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the factors that impact their wellbeing. Individual-level assessments can help identify specific personal and professional factors that contribute to the wellbeing of teachers, including workload, support from colleagues and supervisors, and access to professional development opportunities. This can allow for the development of tailored interventions that address individual needs and promote wellbeing. At the school level, assessments can help identify areas that may require more attention and resources to promote the wellbeing of teachers, such as improving school culture, providing opportunities for professional development, and promoting balance between work and life. This can help guide efforts to promote positive work environments and ultimately improve the quality of teaching and learning in schools. Continued research in this area is crucial to better understanding the complex interplay between various factors that impact the wellbeing of teachers and to developing effective interventions that promote wellbeing and job satisfaction among teachers. Ultimately, improving the wellbeing of teachers can have a positive impact on students' outcomes and the overall effectiveness of schools.

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Role of Administrators in Promoting Positive School Environment For Tutors and Student Well-Being: A Case Study of Some Schools in Ghana

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Abstract: Creating a positive school environment that promotes the well-being of students is an essential aspect of education. Teachers and administrators are instrumental in shaping this environment. The study investigates the role of administrators in fostering a positive school environment and supporting teachers and students at schools in Ghana's Volta Region. The study was underpinned by the theory of Social-Emotional Learning (SEL). Social-Emotional Learning (SEL) theory helps teachers and administrators understand their role in fostering a positive school climate and student well-being. Social and emotional skills are crucial to academic and personal success, according to this view. The study employed a case study approach as its research design. Interviews were conducted with 10 informants who were carefully selected from the basic to the tertiary institutions in Ghana. The study findings indicate that creating a culture of respect, inclusion, and collaboration among students, teachers, and administrators is essential for fostering a positive school environment. Teachers and administrators can promote student well-being by offering emotional and psychological support, promoting healthy habits and lifestyles, and fostering a secure and supportive learning environment. The study emphasises the significance of ongoing professional development for teachers and administrators to equip them to effectively promote a positive school environment and support the well-being of students.

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Administrators, Teachers, Students, Positive Schools' Environments, Well-Being

Introduction

The significance of school administrators in fostering a favourable school atmosphere and aiding in the welfare of educators and learners is of utmost significance. The examination of the contributions made by administrators in selected schools towards the creation of a favourable learning environment is imperative in the Volta Region of Ghana, where education plays a pivotal role in the region's socio-economic development. The present study investigates the distinct approaches utilised by administrators within the Volta Region to cultivate a favourable school atmosphere and augment the welfare of educators and learners. Scholarly literature has consistently emphasised the significant impact of school administrators in shaping the overall school climate (Evertson & Weinstein, 2013; Leithwood, Louis, Anderson, & Wahlstrom, 2004). The overall climate and well-being of a school are significantly influenced by the leadership styles, decision-making practises, and interactions of its staff and students. Research has indicated that

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proficient leadership exhibited by administrators can augment teacher job satisfaction, motivation, and instructional practises, which in turn can result in better student outcomes and well-being (Bass, 1990; Leithwood et al., 2004). The present study centres on the Volta Region of Ghana and aims to investigate the approaches and techniques utilised by educational administrators to cultivate a favourable educational milieu. The Volta Region encounters distinctive obstacles, such as restricted resources and varied socio-cultural circumstances, that require a thorough investigation of how administrators manage these challenges to establish an ideal educational setting. The objective of this study is to gain insights into effective practises that foster a positive school climate and promote the well-being of tutors and students in the Volta Region. This will be achieved by analysing the specific initiatives and leadership approaches implemented by administrators. The results of this study have the potential to provide valuable insights for policymakers and practitioners, thereby facilitating improvements in educational experiences and outcomes within the region.

Statement of the Problem

The significance of school administrators in fostering a favourable school atmosphere and aiding educators and learners is imperative for upholding educational excellence in the Volta Region of Ghana. Notwithstanding the importance of the contributions made by administrators, there exists a dearth of extensive research that delves into the precise tactics employed by administrators in certain schools located in the Volta Region with the aim of cultivating a favourable school atmosphere and augmenting the welfare of educators and learners. The extant body of literature highlights the significant influence of administrators in moulding the school milieu and its effects on the well-being of teachers and students (Evertson & Weinstein, 2013; Leithwood et al., 2004). Nonetheless, the Volta Region context presents distinctive challenges, including but not limited to scarce resources and heterogeneous socio-cultural settings, that have not been extensively investigated in the existing literature. The identified gap in research calls for a thorough investigation into the methodologies and approaches utilised by school administrators in specific educational institutions located in the Volta Region. The objective is to facilitate the cultivation of a favourable school atmosphere. The objective of this study is to provide insight into effective strategies that promote the well-being of teachers and students in the region by examining the distinct initiatives, leadership styles, and decision-making methods employed by administrators. The study's results would offer significant contributions to the understanding of the responsibilities of administrators in fostering a favourable educational setting and enhancing the welfare of educators and learners in the Volta Region. The observations possess the potential to shape educational policies and practises. This can aid educational administrators, policymakers, and stakeholders in devising focused interventions and initiatives that augment the educational encounters and achievements in the locality.

Research Questions

The study was guided by four research Questions.

1. What Are the Perceptions of Students Towards the Roles of School Administrators?
2. How do school administrators' leadership styles impact the overall school climate and well-being of students and teachers?
3. How do school administrators handle challenges of balancing academic performance and needs of teachers and students?
4. What are the most effective strategies for school administrators to promote a positive school environment to support teachers and students' well-being?

Literature Review

Theoretical Framework

The study was underpinned by theory of Social-Emotional Learning (SEL) which had been developed and expanded upon by multiple scholars and researchers. One of the leading proponents of SEL theory is Daniel Goleman, who introduced the concept of Emotional Intelligence (EI) in his book "Emotional Intelligence: Why It Can Matter More Than IQ" (1995). Goleman's work has been influential in highlighting the importance of social and emotional skills in individuals' success and well-being, both in personal and professional contexts. He argues that EI is a crucial component of success and that it can be developed and enhanced through education and training.

The theory of Social-Emotional Learning (SEL) provides a strong foundation for understanding the role of teachers and administrators in promoting a positive school environment and supporting student well-being. This theory emphasizes the importance of developing students' social and emotional competencies, which are essential for their academic and personal success (Eser, 2022).

Research has shown that a positive school environment, characterized by supportive relationships, clear expectations, and opportunities for meaningful engagement, is crucial for students' well-being and academic achievement. Teachers and administrators play a critical role in creating such an environment, and the SEL approach provides them with a framework for doing so. For example, in a study conducted by Durlak et al. (2011), the researchers examined the impact of SEL programs on students' academic achievement, social-emotional skills, and behavior. The study involved a meta-analysis of 213 studies that implemented SEL programs in schools. The findings revealed that SEL programs significantly improved students' academic achievement and social-emotional competencies and reduced negative behaviors such as aggression and substance abuse. These findings highlight the importance of promoting a positive school environment and supporting student well-being through SEL. Teachers and administrators can create such an environment by implementing SEL programs and strategies that focus on developing students' social and emotional competencies. This could involve teaching students' self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, relationship skills, and responsible decision-making.

Furthermore, the SEL approach aligns with the current research on brain development, which highlights the critical role of social and emotional experiences in shaping the brain's architecture. Therefore, teachers and administrators who promote a positive school environment and support student well-being through SEL are not only contributing to students' academic success but also to their lifelong well-being.

Perceptions of Students Towards the Roles of School Administrators. Hakki and Kalayci's (2013) investigated the relationship between students' perceptions of the quality of school life and their level of school engagement. A research investigation was carried out on a cohort of 410 pupils who attended ten educational institutions situated in the central regions of Cankiri province during the academic period of 2011–2012. The respondents completed the 'Scale for School Engagement' and the 'Scale for Quality of School Life'. The data underwent analysis utilizing various statistical techniques, including arithmetical mean, standard deviation, percentage, frequency, correlation, and regression. The research findings suggest a significant correlation between students' perceptions of the quality of school life and their level of school engagement.

Karata, and Ismet (2015) investigated how school administrators view school counsellors and their responsibilities. The study discovered that while school administrators typically see counselling services favourably and work cooperatively with counsellors, there is disagreement among administrators regarding the duties and goals of school counsellors. To improve the efficiency and efficacy of school counsellors, the study contends that it is critical to look into the attitudes and perceptions of school administrators regarding counsellors.

Kartal (2016) examined institutional culture. 56 school administrators who were chosen

based on the volunteering concept participated in the study. The researcher created an interview form to collect the data, which was then subjected to content analysis. The results imply that school administrators have mixed feelings about their institutional culture and cultural diversity. The study concluded that the environment plays a significant role in defining culture. Naidoo (2019) contended that one of the causes of the ongoing deterioration in student performance and the subpar educational outcome in public schools is the inadequate leadership exhibited by many principals. The study investigates how teachers and members of the school management team view the leadership skills displayed by principals who hold the Advanced Certificate in Education: School Leadership and Management (ACESLM) credential. The results show that because of active teaching and learning, principal leadership development is essential for school improvement. The study highlighted the value of formal education in strengthening career development programmes for current and future South African principals.

Administrators' Leadership Styles that Impact the Overall School Climate and Well-Being of Students and Teachers. Amedome (2018) investigated the potential impact of leadership style on the climate of several Senior High Schools in the Hohoe Municipal in Ghana's Volta Region. The study aims to determine the dominant leadership philosophies used by senior high school heads in the chosen schools, to learn how teachers viewed those philosophies, to assess the organisational climate of the chosen schools, and to determine the relationship between leadership philosophies and school climate. The study found that the heads of the chosen SHS tended to utilise democratic leadership styles, that the school atmosphere in the chosen schools was favourable, and that there was an inverse link between the school climate and the leadership style of the head. According to the study's findings, senior high school heads who have been at their current institution for more than ten years should be transferred to another, they should continue taking educational leadership courses, teachers should take in-service courses in educational leadership, and heads should involve teachers and students in decision-making in all situations involving school administration to promote a positive learning environment.

Simbre et al (2023) examine how students perceive the school climate in relation to the leadership styles used by school administrators. The study included 1018 participants, including 907 students and 111 school administrators from 24 different schools. It was conducted using a mixed-methods research approach. The most prevalent leadership style among school administrators was identified using the Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire (MLQ), while student opinions of the school climate were evaluated using the SCAI Secondary General Version. According to the study, inspirational motivation, management by exception, contingent rewards, and transformational leadership are the most common forms of leadership, while laissez-faire, idealised influence, and intellectual stimulation are the least common. Only two out of forty-two connections between leadership style and school climate were significant, according to the study. The study states that in order to establish the optimal learning environment, which will enhance the calibre of teaching and learning and, ultimately, school performance, school administrators and teachers need to understand the amount of transformational leadership and the school climate.

Challenges School Administrators Face in balancing Academic Performance and Needs of Teachers and Students. McBrayer, et al (2018) explored the need for integrated models of leadership in education and identifies four leadership philosophies: transformational, transactional, instructional, and inspiring. The report also highlights how leadership style affects student learning and achievement as well as its function in fostering a healthy school culture. Wise (2015) study sheds light on the difficulties experienced by principals of US public schools. Over 10,000 US principals were chosen at random to receive a survey from the authors, and written replies from a representative sample were then examined for content and themes. According to the findings, principals are currently dealing with a variety of new obstacles in education, such as the

devastating consequences of poverty, mounting demands on students' academic performance, the disintegration of communities, a lack of funding, and a lot of other problems. These principals' opinions imply that we must completely re-evaluate our administration training programmes. The report further notes that although the poll received fewer replies than those indicated above, other notable problems were also raised by the principals who responded.

Andrew et al(2020) investigated the impact of these challenges on the academic achievement of pupils. The research highlights a range of obstacles, including inadequate funding, inadequate collaboration with educational stakeholders, excessive student enrollment, insufficient infrastructure, insufficient teaching and learning resources, and a scarcity of educators. The challenges have had an adverse impact on the academic achievements of both educational institutions and students, resulting in increased rates of student absenteeism. The study suggests that educational stakeholders should increase their investment in education through the implementation of diverse income-generating activities within schools, construction of school infrastructures, and provision of additional funding to schools.

Effective Strategies for School Administrators to Promote a Positive School Environment. Elfrink, et al (2017). discussed a pilot study of the Positive Education Programme, a whole-school strategy for promoting children's wellbeing and fostering a supportive learning environment in Dutch primary schools. The curriculum takes a competency skill enhancement approach with a focus on fostering children's strengths and uplifting moods. A process and impact evaluation of the program's implementation in two schools is part of the study. The evaluation looks at how PEP was implemented, how participants interacted with important elements, and how PEP affected the programming. The results show that parents and staff have generally favourable sentiments about PEP's essential elements. Preliminary data from standardised surveys shows that PEP has a beneficial effect on students' self-reported well-being and problem behaviour, teachers' understanding of students' strengths, and the general mood of the classroom. The distribution of doable tactics and resource materials with an activity focus was regarded as crucial to the continued PEP implementation. The study concludes that greater investigation of the effectiveness of PEP in comparison to "business as usual" is required.

Kuo, and Wang, (2019) contended that effective teaching and student well-being can both be enhanced by instructors' employment of positive disciplining techniques. Teenage learners with learning difficulties and special education teachers in Taiwan were the subjects of the study. The authors employed structural equation modelling to assess the data and created a scale for rating positive discipline tactics. The findings confirmed the hypothesised model and showed a connection between effective classroom management and better student and teacher performance. The relevance of special educators utilising positive discipline techniques is emphasised in the report.

Method

Research Design

The study used a qualitative case study as its method. An in-depth examination of a specific person, group, or organisation in its natural environment is the focus of a case study, a qualitative research design (Yin, 2018). A case study is, in the words of Creswell (2014), "an empirical inquiry that investigates a contemporary phenomenon within its real-life context, especially when the boundaries between phenomenon and context are not clearly evident." Case studies are frequently used in social science research, especially in areas like business, psychology, and education, to develop new theoretical insights and to obtain a deeper knowledge of complicated events.

Population and Sample size

The targeted population of the study was selected school administrators, teachers and

students in educational institutions in the Volta region. These includes administrators at the five (5) pre-tertiary, two (2) tertiary institutions and some officers in the Ghana Education Service (GES) at Kpando.

The study used purposive sampling techniques to sample 10 respondents which include eight administrators, and two students.

Ethical Procedures

In this study all rules were followed stated in the directive of Scientific Research and Publication Ethics of Higher Education Institutions. All participants took part anonymously and voluntary in the survey.

Results

Figure 1. Central Theme, Main Themes and Sub-Themes Showing Administrators Roles in Promoting Positive School Environment in Selected Schools in Volta Region.

Mind Map

The informants' ideas were also brainstormed using the mind map (Zamawe, 2015). The thinking level from a single theme is depicted in a mind map, which is casually provided promptly and spontaneously (McNiff, 2016; Richards, 2002). In the meanwhile, a mind map can be utilized to explore the thematic exposures. The study explored Perceptions of students towards the roles of school administrators, administrators' leadership styles impact the overall school climate and well-being of students and teachers, how do school administrators handle challenges of balancing academic performance and needs of teachers and students and the most effective strategies for school administrators to promote a positive school environment to support teachers and students' well-being. As a result, there is a central theme; administrators' role in ensuring positive school environment, four themes and three sub-themes each under the themes. These variables aid the determining administrator's role is ensuring positive schools' environment.

Figure 2: Word Cloud

Word Cloud

The results are also presented in the form of word cloud by applying a word frequency query (McNiff, 2016; Richards, 2002). Word clouds show the most used and repeated words in the thematic analysis (Zamawe, 2015). Thematic analyses of the present study show that the words such as: school, students, teachers, administrators, and leadership academic styles environment, needs, positive, promote, climate were most used. The size of the word shows its frequency during the interviews.

What Are the Perceptions of Students Towards the Roles of School Administrators?

The first research question sought to explore the perceptions students have towards the roles of school administrators. The respondents were of the view that administrators' roles are very vital to the success of every educational institution this is because for an educational institution to progress or retrogress it all depends on how effective administrators play their roles and discharge their duties well and diligently. Three sub-themes were generated from the views of the respondents as to what they think administrators' roles were. These are the Ensuring Academic Excellence, Ensuring Discipline, Managing and maintaining healthy school.

Ensuring Academic Excellence

The first sub-theme was generated under research question 1(theme one) was that one of the roles of administrators as perceived by students was to ensure that they maintain academic excellence in their institutional roles including making sure necessary resources and logistics available to ensure effective continuous teaching and learning to go on to ensure students maximum academic achievement. Below are some of the views respondents expressed:

Admin001 for instance said that:

“These students may view administrators as individuals who can help them with personal or academic issues.”

Admin009 added that:

“Students may not necessarily have common perceptions of the roles of a school Administrator. This notwithstanding, every student expects a school administrator to project the school as one of the best if not the best by working towards excellent academic performance.”

Ensuring Discipline

The second sub-theme was generated under research question 1(theme one) was that another role of administrators as perceived by students was to perform disciplinary roles in their institution, these disciplinary roles includes administrators set rules, enforce consequences, reinforce positive behavior, maintain open lines of communication, teach conflict resolution skills, provide professional development opportunities, collaborate with support staff, involve students in the disciplinary process, engage parents and guardians in the process, and implement school-wide initiatives to promote positive behavior, character development, and a sense of community. Below are some of the views respondents expressed:

Admin 001 for instance stated that:

“Many students view school administrators as primarily responsible for maintaining discipline within the school environment. They may see them as enforcers of rules and regulations, and as individuals who have the power to punish or reward students based on their behaviour.”

Admin 004 also added that:

“They are just difficult and unwilling to help.”

In support Admin 004, Admin 007 said that:

“They are Strict.”

Similarly, to Admin 001, Admin 009 added that:

“Students may not necessarily have common perceptions of the roles of a school Administrator. This notwithstanding, every student expects a school administrator to project the school as one of the best if not the best by working towards excellent academic performance. To achieve this, students expect the Administrator to ensure discipline among both staff and students, ensure the provision of the necessary facilities and materials for academic work, ensure effective monitoring and supervision.”

Managing and Maintaining School

The third sub-theme was generated under research question 1(theme one) was that another role of administrators as perceived by students was to main and manage the school environment in their institution, The efficient management and upkeep of the school environment by administrators is crucial in establishing an ideal atmosphere that promotes academic success, cultivates a favorable school ethos, and guarantees the general welfare of the school populace. Below are some of the views of respondents expressed:

Admin 001 & Admin 005

“The role is an important one. Other students may perceive school administrators as a support system, who are available to listen to their concerns, offer advice, and provide guidance.”

Admin 010 added that:

“They are supporting staff to management and office.”

Similarly, Admin 002 also indicated that:

“Students' perceptions of school administrators are varied and influenced by individual experiences, school culture, and personal beliefs. Generally, administrators are viewed as responsible for managing and maintaining the school, but some students may see them as supportive while others view them as distant and rule oriented. The perception of school administrators is complex and can differ among students due to various factors.”

Admin008 also posited that:

“Students perceive administrators as officers who should see to the administration of the school in terms of official duties but not to control their behaviour.”

How do school administrators’ leadership styles impact the overall school climate and well-being of students and teachers?

The second research question sought to explore school administrators’ leadership styles employed in the running of their schools which impact the overall school climate and well-being of students and teachers. The respondents were of the view that leadership the efficacy of leadership styles can be contingent upon the distinct circumstances and requirements of the educational institution. Administrators who exhibit adaptability in their leadership style in accordance with the unique circumstances of the school, and consistently display effective leadership practices, possess the capacity to significantly influence the school climate and the welfare of both students and educators in a positive manner. These are creating conducive environment, nature of leadership, readiness to support administrators’ goal.

Creating Conducive Environment

The first sub-theme was generated under research question 2(theme two) was that another role of administrators as perceived by students was creating conducive learning environment in their institution. Through the fulfilment of these duties, educational administrators establish a milieu that facilitates the advancement, involvement, and holistic welfare of students, thereby cultivating a constructive and efficacious educational setting within academic institutions. Below are some of the views respondents expressed:

Admin005 for instance said that:

“Administrators make the learning environment a friendly one.”

Similarly, Admin 008 stated that administrators’ leadership style

“Will impact the school climate and well-being of teachers and students in the since that the nature of leadership styles determines the output of the people living in the academic environment.”

Nature of Leadership

The second sub-theme was generated under research question 2(theme two) was that another role of administrators as perceived by students was the nature of leadership style they employed in the discharge in their duties. It is noteworthy that leadership styles may encompass a combination of various approaches, and proficient administrators frequently modify their style to suit diverse circumstances and the requirements of their educational institution. The selection of a particular leadership style can have a substantial influence on the culture, motivation, and overall welfare of both educators and students within the educational institution. Below are some of the views respondents expressed:

Admin001 outline the various leadership styles an administrators use for instance:

“Authoritative leadership: Administrators who adopt an authoritative leadership style tend to be more focused on maintaining order and control. While this style can be effective in promoting discipline and structure, it can also create an environment that feels authoritarian and hierarchical. Students and teachers may feel disempowered and less likely to speak up or take initiative. Transformational leadership: Administrators who adopt a transformational leadership style focus on inspiring and motivating others to achieve their full potential. This style emphasizes collaboration, communication, and the development of a shared vision. This type of leadership can have a positive impact on school climate, as students and teachers feel more supported and empowered to take on challenges and pursue their goals. Servant leadership: Administrators who adopt a servant leadership style prioritize the needs of others above their own. This style is characterized by a focus on empathy, active listening, and support for others. This type of leadership can promote a positive school climate by creating a culture of caring and support that values the well-being of all members of the school community. Transactional leadership: Administrators who adopt a transactional leadership style focus on

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rewarding good behaviour and punishing bad behaviour. While this approach can be effective in promoting discipline and structure, it can also create an environment that feels punitive and impersonal. Students and teachers may feel less motivated to take risks and may be less likely to view mistakes as opportunities for growth."

Tutors 003 also indicated that his administrator's leadership styles is:

"Very good because administrators interact freely with them to solve their personal problems."

Also, Admin004 stated that:

"It either makes both tutors and students are motivated by positive leadership styles of administrators or demotivated by a negative leadership style."

To support Admin004, Admin009 also added that:

"There are different leadership styles and there is no perfect leadership style for the school administrator to use. Every situation with the type of leadership style that the administrator should use. It is therefore important for school administrators to know about the various leadership styles available to them and the one to use in a particular situation to promote a positive school climate for both students and teachers. These leadership styles include autocratic, Democratic, laissez faire among others."

Similarly, Admin002 also stated that:

"School administrators' leadership styles can positively or negatively impact school climate and the well-being of students and teachers. Transformational leadership styles that prioritize collaboration, inspiration, and innovation can create a positive school environment, while authoritarian or micromanaging styles can create a negative culture. The leadership style adopted by administrators influences the level of support, empowerment, and engagement felt by teachers and students."

Admin008 added that.

"Administrators' choice of leadership style will impact the school climate and well-being of teachers and students in the since that the nature of leadership styles determines the output of the people living in the academic environment."

Readiness to support administrators Goal.

The third sub-theme were generated under research question 2(theme two) was that another impact of administrators' leadership style was readiness of teacher and students to support administrators' goal. Through the implementation of effective leadership strategies, educational administrators can cultivate a sense of preparedness and motivation among both students and educators, thereby facilitating the achievement of their objectives. The preparedness of individuals is demonstrated by their eagerness to participate actively, cooperate, and assume responsibility for their duties, ultimately leading to the attainment of common goals within the academic institution. Below is the view respondent expressed:

Admin010 for instance said:

"Students and teachers feel safe and ready to offer any assistance when needed."

How do school administrators handle challenges of balancing academic performance and needs of teachers and students?

The third research question sought to examine school administrators handle challenges of balancing academic performance and needs of teachers and students. The respondents were of the view that Administrators should foster open lines of communication and collaboration between administrators, teachers, and students, provide ongoing professional development opportunities for teachers, promote differentiated instruction, allocate resources strategically to support both academic performance and the needs of teachers and students, and provide and promote student support services. Administrators should use data to inform decision making related to academic performance and teacher and student needs. They should recognize and celebrate achievements, be flexible and adaptable, engage stakeholders, and promote a culture of continuous improvement

to balance academic performance and the needs of the school community. These are creating conducive environment, nature of leadership, readiness to support administrators' goal. These are being strict in the discharge of duties, effective use of school resources, and prioritization of beneficial actions.

Being strict in the discharge of duties

The first sub-theme was generated under research question 3(theme three) of challenges administrators faced in balancing academic performance and needs of teachers and students is administrators are being strict in the discharge of duties. Strict administrators face resistance and opposition from teachers, students, and other staff members who may perceive their strictness as harsh or inflexible. To mitigate these perceptions, administrators need to ensure their actions and decisions are transparent, consistent, and based on established rules and policies. Additionally, they need to balance discipline with empathy and understanding to foster a supportive and trusting environment. Finally, they need to demonstrate positive outcomes of their strictness to gain the trust and support of the community.

Below are the views expressed by respondents:

Admin009 & Admin008 for instance stated that:

“Some administrators in handling challenges becomes hard on teachers. Some administrators also become authoritative and intolerant towards both teachers and students”.

Effective use of school resources

The second sub-theme was generated under research question 3(theme three) of challenges administrators faced in balancing academic performance and needs of teachers and students is administrators are the effective use of school resources. The respondents were of the view that Administrators must balance limited budgets, increasing costs, competing needs and priorities, inequitable resource distribution, staffing challenges, technological advancements, sustainability and long-term planning, and stakeholder expectations to maximize the impact of available resources. They must prioritize and make difficult decisions to maximize the impact of available resources, navigate competing demands, ensure equitable resource distribution, recruit, and retain qualified staff, manage technological advancements, consider sustainability and long-term planning, and manage stakeholders' expectations.

Below are the view respondents expressed:

Admin010 for instance said that:

‘It's important for the school administrator to manage the limited resources to ensure good academic work.’

In support of Admin010, Admin002 stated that:

“School administrators must find ways to provide adequate resources, support, and training to teachers while also implementing strategies to enhance student learning outcomes.”

Prioritization of beneficial actions

The third sub-theme was generated under research question 3(theme three) of challenges administrators faced in balancing academic performance and needs of teachers and students is administrators are the effective use of school resources. The respondents were of the view that Administrators must navigate through multiple demands and needs to prioritize actions that will have the most positive impact on student learning and well-being. They must balance limited resources with identified priorities, manage stakeholders' expectations, allocate their time efficiently, stay informed about the latest trends and developments, analyze data effectively, and address resistance to change. To do this, they must communicate the rationale behind the prioritized actions, provide support and resources, and foster a culture of collaboration and

continuous improvement. Below are the views respondents expressed:

Admin001 for instances stated that:

“School administrators can balance academic performance with the needs of teachers and students by setting clear expectations, providing professional development opportunities, creating a supportive school culture, prioritizing communication, and making data-driven decisions. By taking a holistic approach to education, administrators can help create a school environment that fosters academic success and meets the needs of all stakeholders.”

Admin003 also added that:

“Administrators’ action are very good because administrators interact freely with them to solve their personal problems.”

In support of Admin003, Admin005 said administrators performed beneficial action:

“Through guidance and counselling services.”

Similarly, tutor002 also added that:

“School administrator in addressing these needs may promote the activities of guidance and counselling, chaplaincy, staff welfare association that would help to address the needs. General needs within the school environment may cover limited resources such as classrooms, teaching and learning materials, finance, staff bungalows, teacher professional development among others The administrator can also put measures in place to encourage teachers to take advantage of courses that would enhance their professional development. Again, the administrator should work closely with stakeholders in addressing the needs of teachers and students for excellent academic performance.”

Admin002 viewed that:

“They must navigate various competing demands and prioritize actions that will benefit the school community. This requires a balance between setting high academic standards and supporting the well-being of students and teachers. Effective communication, collaboration, and a focus on student-centered approaches can help administrators balance these competing demands successfully”.

What are the most effective strategies for school administrators to promote a positive school environment to support teachers and students’ well-being?

The fourth research question 4 (theme 4) sought to determine the most effective strategies for school administrators to promote a positive school environment to support teachers and students’ well-being. The respondents were of the view that administrators’ effective strategies include by fostering respect, empathy, and tolerance, administrators should create a welcoming and inclusive educational environment. They should prioritize professional development opportunities for instructors, as well as emotional and mental health support for both teachers and kids. They should also keep open and encouraging lines of communication with teachers, students, and parents. A safe and loving physical environment should be provided by administrators, who should also involve children in decision-making, celebrate and recognize accomplishments, and involve teachers, students, and other stakeholders in the decision-making process. This fosters a supportive learning environment based on common values and objectives. Three sub-themes were generated from the views of the respondents as to what they think administrators’ roles were. These are variation of appropriate leadership styles, promotion of positive school environment and effective supervision and monitoring.

Variation of appropriate leadership styles

The first sub-theme was generated under research question 4(theme three) of most effective strategies for school administrators to promote a positive school environment to support teachers and students’ well-being is the variation of appropriate leadership style. The respondents were of the view that Administrators should consider the unique requirements of their school community and shape their approach to leadership accordingly. Positive school climate and staff and student

well-being can be fostered through a combination of various leadership approaches that are tailored to individual circumstances. Leaders at educational institutions need to be flexible and sensitive, realizing that diverse people and situations call for unique methods of inspiring and guiding them. Below is the view respondent expressed:

Admin007 for instance stated that:

“They need to be democratic”.

In support of the Admin007, Admin009 added that :

“They should listen to divergent views from both teachers and students and handle them with care to promote a conducive academic environment. Also, school administrators must blend aspects of different leadership styles in handling students and teachers to achieve academic excellence and well being of both teachers and students.”

Admin008 opined that:

“Also, school administrators must blend aspects of different leadership styles in handling students and teachers to achieve academic excellence and well-being of both teachers and students.”

Promotion of positive school environment

The second sub-theme was generated under research question 4(theme three) of most effective strategies for school administrators to promote a positive school environment to support teachers and students' well-being is Promotion of positive school environment. The respondents were of the view that to foster a culture of continuous improvement, administrators should provide opportunities for professional development, establish clear expectations and values, promote positive relationships, foster student engagement and leadership, promote family and community engagement, and place a high priority on social and emotional well-being. These activities will encourage respect, kindness, inclusivity, and a strong work ethic while fostering a healthy school culture. Administrators should also support teachers' professional development, promote a culture of continuous improvement, encourage student leadership and engagement, promote family and community involvement, and place a high priority on social and emotional well-being. Below is the view respondent expressed:

Admin010 for instance stated that:

“Involving students and teachers in decisions related to their well-being.”

Admin002 also added that:

“To promote a positive school environment that supports teachers and students' well-being, school administrators can adopt several effective strategies. These include creating a shared vision for the school, prioritizing communication, and collaboration, fostering a culture of trust and respect, promoting teacher empowerment and development, supporting student social-emotional learning, and providing adequate resources and support to teachers. By implementing these strategies, administrators can create a supportive and inclusive school environment that promotes student and teacher success and well-being.”

In support to Admin010, Admin008 added that:

“They should listen to divergent view from both teachers and students and handle them with care to promote a conducive academic environment.”

Effective supervision and monitoring

The three sub-themes were generated under research question 4(theme three) of most effective strategies for school administrators to promote a positive school environment to support teachers and students' well-being is Effective supervision and monitoring. The respondents were of the view that Teachers should receive regular input from administrators, who should also observe classes, offer professional development opportunities, and set performance objectives. Regular feedback enables teachers to make the required corrections and makes them feel

encouraged. Observations, which can be formal or informal, offer perceptions into both areas of strength and progress. Instructional tactics, classroom management practices, and social-emotional learning can all be the subjects of professional development. Administrators should keep tabs on students' development, encourage data-informed decision making, support collaborative learning environments, highlight, and celebrate triumphs, and foster a good school culture that encourages grit, creativity, and student success. This fosters a supportive learning environment where the success of the students is valued. Below is the view of a respondent expressed:

Admin001 stated that:

“School administrators can foster a sense of community, encourage professional development, prioritize mental and physical health, celebrate successes, foster a positive school climate, and support student engagement. Promoting a positive school environment to support teachers and students' well-being requires a multifaceted approach.”

Discussion and Conclusions

The responses from the participants on the perception of schools administrators attest to the fact that students perception about their school administrator varies and depend on the students experiences he or she have about their school administrators general most of the respondent views were that students perceived administrators role to be a positive one, which would ensure academic discipline and maintain academic achievement standards of the highest standards at the same time maintain a positive environment such success to thrive. The views expressed are in line with Kartal (2016) assertion that the environment plays a significant role in defining culture and administrators must ensure the schools environment is conducive to promoting academic activities. Hakki and Kalayci's (2013) posited that a significant correlation between students' perceptions of the quality of school life and their level of school engagement in the school environment when school administrators are very discharge their duties diligently and effectively.

The responses from the participants on the how do school administrators handle challenges of balancing academic performance and needs of teachers and students attest to the fact that students, administrators, and teacher viewed indicates that schools administrators must ensure they makes available all the necessary resources, implement ethical and transparent actions to promote excellence in academic performance amid all the challenges they are confronted with The views expressed by respondents are consistent with Wise (2015), findings that , principals are currently dealing with a variety of new obstacles in education, such as the devastating consequences of poverty, mounting demands on students' academic performance, the disintegration of communities, a lack of funding, and a lot of other problems, principals till must ensure their institution goals and objectives are achieved .Similarly Andrew,et al(2020) identified school administrators' management challenges that negatively impact students' academic performance, such as insufficient budgets, poor cooperation with education stakeholders, over-enrolment, infrastructure shortages, teaching and learning resource shortages, and teacher shortages and posited that despite all these challenges there is a need to balance such challenges with teachers and students' needs.

The responses from the participants on the style of leadership style used by school administrators to achieve positive school environment attest to the fact that students, administrators, and teacher views support the democratic leadership style of running the schools while other respondents' views indicate that any positive leadership style like the transformational and situational leadership style which can has also proven to be a good leadership styles as indicated by respondents. The views expressed are in line with Amedome (2018) study that found that the heads of the chosen SHS tended to utilise democratic leadership styles, that the school atmosphere in the chosen schools was favourable, and that there was an inverse link between the school climate and the leadership style of the head. Similarly, Simbre at al (2023) opined that,

inspirational motivation, management by exception, contingent rewards, and transformational leadership are the most common forms of leadership, while laissez-faire, idealised influence, and intellectual stimulation are the least common.

The responses from the participants on the most effective strategies for school administrators to promote a positive school environment to support teachers and students' well-being indicated that school administrators can adopt efficacious measures to cultivate a positive school milieu and bolster the well-being of teachers and students. These measures encompass formulating a collective vision for the school, giving precedence to communication and collaboration, nurturing an environment of trust and reverence, empowering and developing teachers, promoting social-emotional learning among students, and furnishing adequate resources and support to teachers. The views expressed by respondents are consistent with Kuo, and Wang, (2019) assertion that effective teaching and student well-being can both be enhanced by instructors' employment of positive disciplining techniques. Teenage learners with learning difficulties and special education teachers in Taiwan were the subjects of the study. The findings confirmed the hypothesized model and showed a connection between effective classroom management and better student and teacher performance. The relevance of special educators utilizing positive discipline techniques is emphasized by Kuo, and Wang, (2019).

Administrators play a crucial role in fostering a positive school environment and promoting the health of teachers and students. Literature suggests that effective strategies to promote a positive school environment and support teacher and student well-being include fostering positive relationships, providing opportunities for professional development, promoting social and emotional learning, and establishing a culture of trust and respect. However, the implementation of such strategies can vary depending on the context of the school, and more research is required to identify strategies that are effective in various settings. By actively supporting the well-being of teachers and students, school administrators can create a more conducive learning environment that fosters academic success, positive mental health outcomes, and overall well-being for the entire school community.

Recommendations

Based on the study's findings and the specific context of selected schools in Volta Region, the following recommendations can be made to support the role of administrators in promoting a positive school environment and supporting the well-being of teachers and students:

1. To cultivate favourable connections among administrators, teachers, and students, it is recommended to establish occasions for frequent communication and cooperation.
2. Offer professional development programmes that concentrate on social and emotional learning, cultural proficiency, and trauma-informed practises to promote the well-being of both teachers and students.
3. It is recommended that school administrators exhibit favourable social and emotional conduct, such as empathy, kindness, and respect, and foster an environment of trust and respect among the school community.
4. Establish an environment that is conducive to learning by creating a positive and welcoming physical space. This can be achieved through the provision of well-lit and well-ventilated classrooms, comfortable furniture, and aesthetically pleasing decor.
5. It is recommended to establish unambiguous and uniform policies and procedures to manage occurrences of bullying, harassment, or any other types of adverse conduct that could potentially affect the well-being of both students and teachers.
6. One potential strategy is to introduce a comprehensive social and emotional learning

curriculum across the entire school, which would aim to equip students with fundamental life skills, including but not limited to communication, empathy, and problem-solving.

7. It is recommended to offer mental health services and resources, such as counselling and therapy, to promote the mental health and well-being of both students and teachers.
8. It is recommended to carry out periodic surveys and assessments to oversee and appraise the efficacy of the educational institution's endeavours to foster a favourable school milieu and aid both educators and learners in terms of their mental and physical health.

By implementing these recommendations, schools in the Volta Region, can create a more conducive learning environment that promotes teacher and student well-being and academic success.

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Well-Being in Education in Poland

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Abstract: The aim of this paper was to check teachers' satisfaction with work, their emotions, their work environment, their work-life balance, and their access to trainings concerning mindfulness, well-being, and self-development. The work, based on a survey conducted among 102 foreign language (mostly English) teachers of different types of schools (i.e., kindergartens, primary schools, secondary schools, universities, etc.), is concerned with issues related to the well-being of teachers in Poland. Teachers who took part in the quantitative survey between December 2022 and January 2023 gave anonymous answers to the questions concerning their well-being, their attitude to work, their ability to take part in self-development trainings, and their relations at the schools and institutions in which they work. It was planned to find out which teacher groups face more difficulties of different kinds within their working places. The study revealed that teachers who take part in various forms of self-development are more aware of their emotions and ways of dealing with stress than those who do not. Those who work in towns and villages are happier than those who work in cities. Those who work with many pupils suffer from the incessant noise and even rude behaviour of their students. Finally, it was concluded that happier and less stressed teachers, who are able to maintain work-life balance and work in a friendly environment, may become better teachers and better learners. Teachers' health and well-being and positive attitude towards life and work are very important due to the fact that any of these attitudes influence the way in which their students acquire knowledge. Happier teachers teach happier and faster-learning students.

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Introduction

Well-being, which according to various definitions, for instance, in the Cambridge Dictionary (2023), means the state of being healthy and happy, is very important in the everyday lives of all of us. In Psychology Today (Davis, 2019), we may find that: "Well-being is the experience of health, [happiness](#), and prosperity. It includes having good mental health, high life satisfaction, a sense of meaning or purpose, and the [ability to manage stress](#). More generally, well-being is just feeling well."

Well-being is very important in education, especially after the post-COVID-19 pandemic period. When students are happy, they learn better and faster; when teachers are happy, they conduct their classes in a better way; and in consequence, everyone feels better and more comfortable, not only those who have to acquire knowledge but also those who share it (Spitzer,

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2012). Teachers are the most important links in the whole process of education due to the fact that they shape it and influence students (Baryła-Matejczuk, 2021). Teaching processes involve huge emotional labour because teachers not only give students directions, definitions, check their work, and explain differences between some phenomena, but teaching is also a huge mental challenge. Teachers have to deal with stress, noise, and sometimes the rude behavior of children or even their parents. Sometimes they work under pressure caused by other teachers or their supervisors. A lot of teachers, especially those working in public, i.e., state, or private schools, do not earn much money. (Dziennik Ustaw, 2023) All those aspects mentioned above may lead to burnout, depression, and various illnesses. When it is necessary, teachers should have support and training. They should be aware of how to deal with emotions, stress. What is more, such or similar help should be provided not only for teachers, but also for students. We all must remember that a happy and healthy teacher most often means a happy and motivated student. Human brains use so-called mirror neurons, which allow us to understand the behaviour of other people, but they also respond to what we observe; they enable the imitation of various emotions such as sadness, happiness, and anger (Vetulani, 2014). Mirror neurons play an important role in human relationships; they are crucial, especially in the field of education (Żylińska, 2013).

Method

The answers of 102 teachers (although some of them did not give answers to all questions) who took part anonymously and voluntarily in the survey are presented below. To begin with, what seems important is that 98% of them claimed that teachers need psychological support at work.

Teachers who took part in the survey between December 2022 and January 2023 are 99% women, mostly between 36 and 45 years old, whereas men constitute only 1%, and their ages vary from 26 to 55 years old.

Figure 1. Teachers' Age

Figure 2. Teachers' Age and Gender

39% of the respondents live in towns smaller than 50 thousand inhabitants, 25% in cities with more than 500 thousand inhabitants, 20% live in villages, 9% in cities between 51 and 500 thousand inhabitants, and 7% in cities with 101 to 500 thousand inhabitants.

They work in towns and cities with the same number of inhabitants, respectively.

Figure 3. Teachers' Place of Living and Gender

Figure 4. Teachers’ Place of Living and Age

16% of the respondents work in kindergartens, 29% in early school education units, 36% in primary schools grades 4–8, 30% in secondary schools, 5% at universities, 1% in art, 2% in musical schools, 8% in language schools, and 15% are freelancers. Among those teachers who work in the schools mentioned above, 85% work in state and public schools, 13% in private schools, 1% in charter schools, and 1% are only self-employed. 76% of the teachers work in only one place, 23% in two places, and 1% in three places.

Figure 5. Teachers’ Place of Work and Gender

43% of the respondents answered that there are between 18-26 students in the classes where they teach; 30% of teachers work in classes with less than 18 students, 19% with more than 26 students in a class. The rest of the teachers work individually or with fewer than 6 students.

54% of teachers answered that classes are divided into groups when it comes to language classes, whereas 46% answered that there is no division. In those cases when there is a division 26% of teachers answered that there are between 10-15 students in a group, 18% said that there are more than 18 students in a group, 11% have fewer than 10 students. However, there are some teachers who have between 12-30 students in a class, because there is no division into groups during ESP (English for Specific Purposes) classes in so-called technical secondary schools. On the diagram below, we may see how the situation concerning division into groups looks during language classes in bigger cities and in smaller towns or villages.

Figure 6. Division Into Groups

According to the received data, language classes are divided into groups more often in towns with less than 50 thousand inhabitants (63%) and cities with more than 500 thousand inhabitants (57%), whereas 80% of the respondents living in villages claimed there is no division.

Ethical Procedures

In this study, all rules were followed as stated in the Directive on Scientific Research and Publication Ethics of Higher Education Institutions. All participants took part anonymously and voluntarily in the survey.

Results

In my survey, I asked teachers a couple of questions concerning their satisfaction and dissatisfaction with work. I asked them what they liked and/or did not like about their job. 77% of teachers answered that they like their work, whereas 22% stated that they do not like their job. Among those who like their work, 31% said that they just like what they do; 8% admitted that they work in a creative environment; 8% are professionally satisfied and fulfilled; and only 3% admitted that they like their job because of their pay. Among those teachers who are not satisfied with their work, only 1% are happy with their salary, and 1 person likes being a teacher because of job security. 2% admitted that although they do not like their job, they work in creative teams.

Only 79 people responded to my question concerning the causes of their dissatisfaction with work. 65% pointed to too many duties, 75% to low salaries, 34% complain about too many students in a class, 25% feel tired and preoccupied with requirements, and 15% work in an

unfriendly working place, 1% complain about the behaviour of their students' parents, 1 % about students' behaviour, 1% are dissatisfied with the school's management, and 1% complain about commuting. Teachers who are satisfied with their job (40%) live in towns with less than 50 thousand inhabitants, whereas those who are satisfied with their job and live in villages constitute 24%, and those who live in cities with more than 500 thousand inhabitants constitute 22% of all respondents.

Figure 7. Teachers Who Are Happy/ Unhappy With Their Jobs

Figure 8. Teachers Who Are Happy/ Unhappy With Their Jobs

48% of the interviewed teachers admitted to taking part in trainings concerning self-

development, mindfulness, and/or breathing techniques, while 46% did not take part in any workshops. Among those teachers who educate themselves, 29% took part in trainings concerning self-development. What is interesting is that such answers were given by women only; most of them (64%) were between 36 and 45 years old. 48% of the respondents (again, only women; 53% work in towns with less than 50 thousand inhabitants) took part in trainings concerning dealing with stress. The respondents also took part in workshops and trainings devoted to breathing techniques (19%), mindfulness (19%), and professional burnout (2%). Within the group of teachers taking part in self-education, 50% said that they had to pay for the courses individually, whereas the remaining 50% had their courses financed by the institutions in which they work. 38% of those who pay individually live in cities with more than 500 thousand inhabitants and 25% in towns with less than 50 thousand inhabitants. Trainings are organised mostly by the Centres for Teachers' Education (46%) and private institutions (56%).

Figure 9. What Did Training Change In Teachers' Lives?

77% of teachers who pay for their further education individually spend on it less than 500 PLN in a year, 11% spend between 500 and 1000 PLN, 9% between 1000 and 2000 PLN, and 3% spend more than 2000 PLN. Those teachers who take part in trainings believe that they are necessary and useful (88%). They claim that thanks to such courses, they learned how to deal with stress and emotions (28%), systematised their knowledge in the field of self-development and stress reduction (28%), made proper decisions concerning their work as well as their private lives (26%), and even made decisions concerning a change of work (9%). Some of the respondents

indicated that they learned how to use their voice properly (2%); some learned how to calm down and realise that they have a problem not only with their work but also with their emotions (2%).

Figure 10. Amount Of Money That Teachers Have To Pay For Their Courses

87% of them admitted that the courses mentioned above are necessary, and 98% stated that they needed psychological support, especially due to the fact that 85% of them claimed they experienced frustration and stress because of work. Among those who are stressed, 41% live in towns with fewer than 50 thousand inhabitants, whereas 38% live in towns and cities with more than 50 thousand inhabitants, and the rest (13%) live in villages. Most of the teachers who feel stressed work in kindergartens and primary schools (56%); the other respondents (33%) work in secondary schools.

Figure 11. Stress at work

Figure 12. Need For Psychological Support

In most cases, the condition of anxiety and stress results in the performance of too many duties and expectations from the headmasters or students' parents (72%); the other reasons specified by the respondents are: low payment (56%), lack of support from the institution as well as students' parents (47%), lack of psychological support for teachers (37%), noise at schools (36%), problems with students' behaviour during lessons (28%), unfriendly atmosphere at work, bad relations with co-workers (21%), lack of access to self-development trainings paid by schools (11%), working in difficult conditions (1%), commuting (1%), and commuting (1%).

When the respondents were asked whether they were able to not think about work in their free time, most of them (85%) answered positively. In order to relax, they meet friends and/or spend their spare time with family (55%), read books (54%), take up sport (31%), visit different places (28%), use nature to fill up their leisure time (1%), sing (1%), listen to music (1%), watch movies on streaming platforms (2%), or perform their hobbies (5%). Unfortunately, there are a few who admit that they do not have any time to relax (1%) and those who cannot find appropriate ways of relaxing.

Figure 13. Free Time Vs Work

Figure 14. Activities In Free Time

Finally, I asked the teachers about the necessity of training concerning mindfulness, and/or other stress-reducing methods for the students they work with. Most of them agreed that such courses are necessary (99%) and that there are courses dealing with concentration, stress reduction in 21% of schools. 53% of such courses are covered by schools, or institutions supervising schools. Children with special needs have access to various classes within their curriculum.

According to 80% of teachers, such classes help students to concentrate on what is difficult and poses problems to them, help them to see their strengths (67%), help them to call and control

their emotions (65%), and teach them creativity (33%).

Teachers who took part in the survey mostly like their jobs (78%) and their answers to questions concerning this issue of "job liking" are really important. Although the respondents do not earn much money (75% complain about this problem), work in incessant noise, with too many students; and have to deal with various problems that may affect their own mental health, they still like their jobs. However, as pointed out earlier, 65% complain about the excess of requirements and duties at schools, bad relations at work; as well as various problems with students or their parents, which in consequence may influence their well-being and result in the growth of stress, various forms of professional burnout; psychological problems; and even depression (Kordziński, 2022).

Discussion and Conclusions

The teachers want to develop themselves, improve their skills; they declare they want to learn new things (how to use their voice, how to breathe properly, how to implement inclusive education, how to maintain optimal classroom settings, etc.). Many teachers argue that training helps them to take proper decisions (concerning both their private life and work); to keep life-work balance, and to become more aware of themselves and/or their emotions, which is really important according to the World Health Organisation (WHO, 2021). A small number of teachers (2%) said that although their work was financially stable and there were not many students in the classes where they taught, the headmasters, principals and/ or school owners used various types of mobbing; they were stressed and mentally exhausted, unable to leave their work. Many of them admitted they had to take part in therapy, thanks to which they were finally able to move forward and find different jobs. 46% of teachers agreed that thanks to such trainings they learned various techniques, such as how to deal with chronic stress, how to function in difficult situations, and how to cope with the various behaviours of students, parents, and/or other co-workers.

On the basis of the answers of the respondents, it is clear that the state of well-being among teachers is crucial to the whole process of education. Those teachers who take part in training, have access to various workshops concerning their self-development and/ or different mindfulness-shaping techniques, who develop themselves, spend time on taking up sports, meeting with friends and family, travelling, keep life-work balance are happier and more able to separate their working conditions from their personal life. Thanks to various creative things that they do after work, such as reading, singing, walking in the forest, being close to nature, listening to music, and watching films, they are able to relax, collect their thoughts, maintain a relatively objective state, and deal with the everyday problems that they have to face at work. When they eat healthy food, perform physical activity, and sleep well, they are more efficient, have more energy, have a sense of purpose in their lives, and feel happier and healthier because their immune system works better (Coyle, 2017). What they still need at work, no matter whether they work in cities, towns, or villages, is psychological support, understanding, and help from their supervisors and co-workers. They also need cooperation with the students' parents, work in conditions that do not expose them to so much noise, smaller numbers of students in groups, or division of the students into groups with less noise, fewer students in groups, or division into groups, especially during language classes. They also need life-work balance conditions in order to take care of their mental health and well-being.

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Design and Implementation of Web Applications for the Well-Being of Children Suffering From Dyslexia

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Abstract: Dyslexia is a specific disability that is difficult to diagnose, even for professionals who deal with health issues. Therefore, it is derived indirectly from the Greek words "dis" and "lexi" [δυσ + λέξις], meaning "difficult word". Dyslexia is a learning disability that impairs a child's reading, writing, and spelling abilities. It is one of the most widespread learning problems, affecting up to 15% of the population, according to estimates. Symptoms of well-being can manifest in various ways, such as difficulty in writing, reading, learning, space orientation, reading aloud, or continuity in speaking. Based on medical sources, dyslexia is very likely inherited, but it is most often identified when the child begins the first stage of education. Primary school children are typically treated using quantitative and qualitative methods that seek early identification of symptoms and support parents and teaching staff in the service of children with dyslexia. In this context, a case study was conducted in the municipality of Prizren, involving students' well-being, parents, teaching staff, administrative staff, and school management. Additionally, a web application was specifically designed for the well-being of this category of students and evaluated by experienced IT experts. The web application is designed to help children with dyslexia improve their phonological awareness, reading speed, and comprehension. It also provides resources and different materials for parents and educators, such as lesson plans and instructional videos. Overall, web applications for dyslexic children's well-being have the potential to enhance their reading and writing abilities, build their self-esteem, and advance their general mental health. We can assist children with dyslexia in overcoming their obstacles and realizing their full potential by creating accessible, interesting, and useful web applications. The research results will show the Republic of Kosovo better and will allow you to have more interest in continuing the research in this field!

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Introduction

Reading and writing difficulties are frequently described in generic terms. Regardless of conventional training, cognitive ability, and social and cultural opportunities, dyslexia presents as a disease that makes it difficult to learn the technique or skill of reading. This phrase is used to characterize a student's particular reading and writing challenges (Bajrami V. , 2008). It can be claimed that neither our society nor educational institutions are well-versed in this issue. Most of the time, it goes unrecognised because of ignorance, but that does not imply that it is not there.

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Individuals with dyslexia will be able to attain literacy norms that are acceptable to their culture with the help of appropriate and timely interventions. While this study shows that dyslexic kids might be difficult, they can also be rewarding. Given that we live in a technological age, it begs the question of why we shouldn't take advantage of the Internet's advantages to obtain the information we require. Due to this exact reason, I have developed a website for teacher's and parent's awareness and well-being in this research, where they can get information from experts in the area and where the concept for the website was first conceived to meet the requirements in a specific location. In this webpage, we make reference to data gathered by experts in the field of speech therapy through the integration of their knowledge, i.e., each expert in his field providing pertinent data that teachers and parents need in the education of the child. My task was to make it easier to obtain this information by developing a website specifically for dyslexia.

Definition, Symptoms, and Information About Dyslexia

The Greek terms "dyslexia" (meaning "weak, unmatched language") and "lexis" (meaning "language, words") are the source of the word (Bajrami M. V.). Dyslexia is a specific learning problem with a neurological basis, according to the official definition. It is characterized by difficulties with spelling and decoding, as well as difficulties with accurately and/or fluently recognizing words. Students with dyslexia typically struggle with other language abilities like spelling, writing, and word pronunciation (Snowling, Hulme, & Nation, 2020). Although dyslexia has an impact on people throughout their lives, that impact might change depending on where they are in life.

The child has severe issues with both writing and reading; he reads numerals and characters backward, such as 15 for 51 and 16 for 61; he also reads letters incorrectly, such as b for d, p for q, m for n, etc. (Perry, Zorzi, & Ziegler, 2019) The child has trouble memorizing the alphabet, the multiplication table, and the order of the days of the week. Dyslexia is not a sickness, and those who have it can achieve it in school and as adults if they work hard, receive the right teaching at the right time, and have support from their family, teachers, friends, and others. (Baschenis, et al., June 29, 2021) A child can receive the right teaching and accommodations to succeed in school as soon as he or she is assessed.

The Social and Emotional Interaction Between Children

One of the first researchers to discuss the emotional elements of dyslexia was Samuel T. Orton, M.D. (Orton, 2023). His research shows that most children who subsequently receive a dyslexia diagnosis are content. Emotional difficulties arise when early reading teaching does not meet their learning needs (Nicholson, 2013): As classmates outpace dyslexic pupils in reading abilities over time, dissatisfaction grows. When we find ourselves in circumstances, we have little or no control over, stress and worry rise. Despite spending numerous hours in specialized programs or working with professionals, many dyslexic people have endured years of frustration and minor achievement. People with dyslexia might have discovered that being around other people increases their chances of making embarrassing blunders and the consequent adverse reactions that may follow. (Bajrami M. V.) Therefore, it makes it natural that many dyslexics are withdrawn, and prefer to hang out with kids or separate themselves from other people. Another common complication of dyslexia is depression. (Bowman & Ed.D. & Vincent Culotta, 2023). Symptoms of depression in children and adolescents may differ from those in depressed adults. It is uncommon for a depressed youngster to appear lethargic or express sadness (Fragel-Madeira, et al., 2015). Instead, in order to mask uncomfortable feelings, he or she may become more busy or mischievous. Case Study: Dyslexia in the Elementary Schools of the Municipality of Prizren.

Method

Case study, one of the qualitative research methods, was used as a method in the study.

Sample of the study is shown in Table 1. In this study all rules were followed stated in the directive of Scientific Research and Publication Ethics of Higher Education Institutions. All participants took part anonymously and voluntary in the survey.

Case Study: Dyslexia in the elementary schools of the Municipality of Prizren

The case study is restricted to the Municipality of Prizren due to the difficulties of conducting research over the full region of the Republic of Kosovo. The study also included elementary schools. The study includes information gathered from teachers at elementary schools.

Results

Results are described in this section. Table 1 summarizes information on participants' gender, age, work experience and their answers to the questions as a percentage.

Table 1: Statistical analysis of data collected by teachers

		Number of participants	Percent
Gender	Male	19	17.1%
	Female	92	82.9%
Age	20-29	14	12.6%
	30-39	28	25.2%
	40-49	39	35.1%
	Over 50	30	27.0%
		6	19
Work experience	6-19	39	35.1%
	Over 20	53	47.7%
		I	25
Which grades do you teach?	II	25	22.5%
	III	27	24.3%
	IV	21	18.9%
	V	13	11.7%
		Yes	54
Have you had the opportunity to work with students suffering from dyslexia during your experience?	No	57	51.4%
How would you describe your experience working with students with dyslexia?	Very little	31	27.9%
	Less	58	52.3%
	Very good	22	19.8%
Does it seem to you that the student often does not concentrate on the lesson, and you do not know the reason?	Yes	72	64.9%
	No	39	35.1%
Do you have difficulty remembering certain tasks?	Yes	80	72.1%
	No	31	27.9%
Do they make "strange" mistakes in reading and writing?	Yes	77	69.4%
	No	34	30.6%
Are there difficulties in the subject of mathematics and do they choose the tasks in a "strange" way?	Yes	61	55.0%
	No	50	45.0%

A dyslexia website's appearance is crucial to its ability to enlighten and support its audience. The website has an eye-catching design that is both polished and interesting. It also has an eye-pleasing color scheme that does not detract from the information. The website also has a clean, well-organized style with readable information and excellent graphics. It has simple navigation, obvious calls to action, and is user-friendly and accessible. This is crucial for dyslexic people who can have trouble with intricate layouts or perplexing user interfaces.

This is what the website looks like, designed for the well-being of children suffering from dyslexia.

KËTU MUND TI GJENI TË DHËNAT

Rreth Disleksisë

Regjistrohu ne faqen tone per me shume info dhe per testin e Disleksise

Figure 1: UI of the web application

Discussion and Conclusions

Comparing the pertinent works that deal with the well-being of dyslexic children (Wilmot, Pizzey et al. 2022) we observe that their primary goal is to explore the socio-emotional experience of growing up with dyslexia from the perspective of the child and the parents (Wilmot, Hasking et al. 2022) the breadth and nature of the literature that investigates the factors that may influence the association between childhood dyslexia and internalizing and externalizing mental health concerns, and other issues (Wilmot, Pizzey et al. 2022). By doing this, a better awareness of self-esteem and mental health in the context of dyslexia is desired, as is a better understanding of parents' own mental health and the need for parent-informed support (Wilmot, Pizzey et al. 2022).

This study aims to highlight the significance of using the Internet and how it may improve people's lives when they use the right web page to find the right information. Based on the aforementioned data, we can see that parents and instructors found the website design to be helpful. In my opinion, the website compiles all of the requests and queries that were not able to receive answered. Therefore, who among the people did not have the chance to confer with experts? They already have a free, open-access website that is available to users around the clock. According to the survey of teachers, we can see that the level of knowledge in the Municipality of Prizren is not adequate, and the instructors' lack of knowledge regarding dyslexia is also reflected in the preliminary figures. In conclusion, web applications have the potential to significantly improve the well-being and quality of life of children suffering from dyslexia. Through the use of specialized web applications, these children can access a range of tools and resources that are specifically designed to help them overcome the challenges associated with dyslexia. From reading and writing aids to speech recognition software and interactive learning tools, web applications can provide children with the support they need to thrive academically and socially, ultimately enhancing their well-being. Moreover, web applications offer a convenient and cost-effective solution for families and educators looking to support children with dyslexia. With many web applications now available for free or at a low cost, they can be easily integrated into existing educational programs, helping to ensure that children with dyslexia receive the support they need to succeed. Overall, the benefits of web applications for the well-being of children with dyslexia are clear. By providing personalized and accessible support, web applications can help these children to develop the skills and confidence they need to succeed both in and out of the classroom, ultimately improving their well-being. As such, the continued development and implementation of web applications for dyslexia represents an important step forward in providing effective

support for children with this common learning difficulty. Finally, we can state that this website will undoubtedly infuse Kosovo with a fresh attitude that will encourage parents and educators to grow personally and learn new information from experts in their industry, ultimately contributing to their well-being.

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Awareness of Politeness Maxim in An Efl Context: A Case in Libya

Ayman Riheel Alnaas Taha ¹

Abstract: Since the beginning of our societies, politeness has been the target of criticism. This criticism begins as early as childhood, and as a direct result, the politeness maxim has developed into an interesting topic of conversation. When we are acting or speaking, we must treat everyone politely. This obligation exists regardless of the context. We can maintain a polite manner in our vocal expressions even though our intentions are not particularly good for the people we speak with. For example, we must respect other people's perspectives, even if we vehemently disagree with them. Within the context of this piece, Leech's aphorisms act as the cornerstone upon which an investigation of civility is built. He recommended six distinct groups of etiquette maxims and provided examples for each. The primary focus of this research is on the extent to which university students in Libya studying English as a foreign language are aware of the need to maintain good manners. According to the abstract, the study's goal is to explore the level of knowledge held by Arab-Libyan and Amazigh-Libyan EFL students about the speech act of politeness maxim. This investigation will be carried out to determine the amount of knowledge possessed by these students. In the classroom of English for Speakers of Other Languages (ESOL), which serves as a learning environment? Because utterances must sound universal and acceptable to contemporary culture, the research recommends investigating the approval and agreement maxim in the English as a Foreign Language (EFL) context. This is because these maxims make ethical sense in education.

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Introduction

The words and expressions people use can impact how they think, say, feel, and connect with others because language is a crucial part of social identity. People utilise various strategies while communicating since it is a crucial part of the communicative skills expected of language users. As a result, this section of the Study contains information about its background, challenges, research questions, and goals. This part also explains the importance of the Study.

Background of the Study

By analysing how Libyan Arab and Amazigh EFL undergraduate students do the speech acts of suggestion, apology, request, permission, opinion, and questioning, the current study aims to ascertain their awareness of the politeness maxim. Utilising the civility maxim is thus one of the communication tactics. Being polite has grown to be an important aspect of society; it is now used to describe the social climate of a town or region. An example of a social norm formed by local customs is politeness. To show that they are civilised people who won't be accused of being rude or having poor manners, they must occasionally act polite. Although politeness can be used to

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pinpoint social culture, it is, in many ways, a universal virtue (Hussain et al.,2022). For example, the modesty maxim calls for the speech participants to be humble by dialling back their admiration for them. As evidence, consider the following exchange between a teacher and his two pupils as they discuss their exam results:

Teacher: Your results are excellent!

Student A: Ah, I think it is ordinary.

Students B: Oh!, it is me.

The answer "**Ah, I think it is ordinary**" from student A is more polite, and it is the answer the listeners expect more. This means that student A humbly minimises praise for herself and maximises disdain for herself, showing modesty. However, the answer of student B, "**Oh! It is me,**" is considered immodest because he maximises praise on himself, showing an attitude of arrogance and immodesty. Therefore, the answer of student A shows the universality of the modesty maxim in terms of humbleness and politeness. In this case, the context can be either situational or cultural. Pragmatics is very important because it teaches people how to behave in society, so many people developed some pragmatic theory to support their communication skills during its development. Geoffrey Leech, with his Politeness Principles (PP) theory, is one of them (Leech, 1983).

Following the Libyan revolution in 2011, many changes occurred in the country's various governmental systems, including the educational system. As a result, there is a need to investigate Libyan EFL undergraduate learners' competence in using English in various discourses and their choice of strategies when expressing speech acts.

The aim of the study

The current research aims to:

1. To examine the awareness of Arab-Libyan and Amazigh-Libyan EFL learners regarding the speech acts of politeness maxim in various social contexts.
2. To investigate the politeness realisation of the participants while producing the speech acts of permission, request, apology, question, opinion, and suggestion.
3. To investigate the similarities and differences between Arab-Libyan and Amazigh-Libyan EFL(non-Arab minority in Libya) users in responding to situations of speech and act patterns.

Research Questions

The research seeks to find answers for the following research questions:

1- To what extent Arab-Libyan and Amazigh-Libyan EFL learners are able to choose the appropriate politeness maxim in performing the speech acts of permission, request, apology, question, opinion .and suggestion.

2- What are the similarities and differences between Arab-Libyan and Amazigh-Libyan EFL learners regarding politeness maxim use and patterns in the speech acts of permission, request, apology, question, opinion .and suggestion.

3 Are there any significant differences regarding the appropriate use of politeness maxim by the Arab-Libyan and Amazigh-Libyan EFL learners?

Statement of Problems

The current study aims to examine the strategies used by a group of Libyan undergraduates in performing the previously mentioned speech acts to investigate whether there are any differences between Arab-Libyan and Amazigh-Libyan EFL learners regarding the appropriate

use of politeness maxims in speech act patterns. It also investigates how effective the politeness maxim has been in Libyan societies. According to the author, language learners can develop their communicative and transcultural competence when linguistic and cultural experiences shape communicative events (Takkula et al. 2008).

Significance of the Study

As a result, the current study's investigation of Arab-Libyan and Amazigh-Libyan EFL learners' interlanguage speech acts is critical in raising stakeholders' understanding of the importance of politeness competence. Furthermore, the findings of this study may provide useful information for improving EFL language learners' communicative ability, and we feel they might serve as a model for future research, especially in the EFL context.

Method

The current chapter provides background information for the study. It reviews the literature of previous studies on the topic and illustrates the theoretical frameworks used. In other words, it primarily explains previous research on speech act theory regarding the politeness maxim and the proposed six maxims of Leech. According to Leech, the Politeness Principle is about minimising the expression of impolite beliefs, with a corresponding positive version of maximising the expression of polite beliefs that is slightly less important. As a result, utilising Leech's Politeness principle, it is feasible to evaluate dialogue between characters in theatre. Leech proposed using politeness to create and understand language. Politeness principles are intended to foster a sense of community and social relationships. In this sense, Leech also proposed six maxims: Tact Maxim, Generosity Maxim, Approval Maxim, Modesty Maxim, Agreement Maxim, and Sympathy Maxim.

Results

Politeness Theory

Politeness theory has garnered considerable interest in pragmatics over the last three decades, and it has evolved into a sub-branch of pragmatics with a close relationship to pragmatics (Thomas, 2014). Politeness is a type of behaviour that is generally revealed in languages and is directly related to societies. Politeness theory implies a type of behaviour or speech that gives advantages to others, and the linguist claims that:

"Face can be further classified into positive face and negative face. A "positive face" alludes to the speaker's desire for acceptance and admiration from others. It puts more emphasis on the speaker's self-esteem. If others ignored him or her, one's face would be in danger. Negative face refers to one's free choice of actions and his desire not to be imposed on by others. It put stress on the freedom of action. The issue of "face" protection always draws attention in cross-cultural communication. Politeness is culture-specific. What one culture considers polite is usually not considered very polite or even rude in another culture. Knowing another country's culture can prevent people from losing face (Jiang, 2015, p. 97). "

However, only some studies of the politeness principle have been published in the literature. It occurred as a result of the fact that the majority of literary works were generated as written text rather than conversation. Literary work is classified into three categories: poetry, prose, and drama. Drama is the only literary work that is written in a conversational style.

Theory of Speech Acts

Speech acts are the specific linguistic functions that something that is stated performs. The father of speech-act theory (SAT), British philosopher J. L. Austin, was the first to explain the idea at Oxford University in a series of lectures between 1952 and 1954. He claimed that when people make utterances, they not only say words; they also do actions with them. Execute the intended actions and ensure that listeners understand the conversation's purpose. According to Austin

(1965), there are three forms of linguistic acts in utterance: the locutionary act (what is said), the illocutionary act (what is meant), and the perlocutionary act (what is meant) (the effect on the hearer). It depends on the situation and the speaker's intention; for example, it could be a picnic tip or a sentence to break the ice, start a conversation, etc. According to Achiba (2003), the illocutionary act is a specific language function performed by an utterance. The third and final type of meaning is perlocutionary, which refers to the effect of the speech act on the listener. Perlocutionary acts, according to Austin (1975), are "what we bring about or achieve by saying something" (p. 109). For example, when producing the same sentence as in the previous example, "It is sunny," only the speaker's facial expressions or voice tone may be sufficient for the hearer to understand the intended meaning. In this sense, Henkemans argues that:

"The modification of the standard theory of speech acts is to make it possible to explain that in practise, arguing is not the same as convincing. Even though the verbal means used in arguing and convincing are the same, the emotional conditions of these acts are different. To account for this difference. There is a need to differentiate between the correctness of a speech act from the speaker's point of view and from the listener's point of view (Henkemans, 2014)."

Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) promoted teaching the target language's culture in the 1970s, and, as a result, using speech acts in an EFL/ESL context aimed to increase teachers' and students' cultural awareness of the target language. Indeed, supporters of CLT argue that teaching a foreign or second language and teaching cultural and social norms cannot be separated and that "speech acts can be realised in different ways in different cultures" (Sanal & Ortactepe, 2019: 378). As a result, taking into account the cultural and social beliefs and norms of the learners' mother tongue society is critical when conducting studies that investigate speech acts, and in this case, the researcher propagates that:

"With regard to speech acts, about half of the research projects have included the original three speech acts (requests, refusals, and apologies); others only included one or two of those three but added other speech acts; and still other projects ignored the speech act issue altogether. Interestingly, one project (Brown & Ahn, 2011) found that speech acts made very little difference in the variance produced by any of their five tests of Korean pragmatics, therefore, while a variety of speech acts should probably be included in instruction as examples of where to pay attention to pragmatics, speech acts may not make much difference when measuring pragmatic competence (Brown, 2018)".

Politeness Principles

According to Leech, the Politeness Principle is about minimising the expression of impolite beliefs, with a corresponding positive version of maximising the expression of polite beliefs that is slightly less important. Leech proposed using politeness to create and understand language. Politeness principles are intended to foster a sense of community and social relationships. Tact Maxim, Generosity Maxim, Approval Maxim, Maxim, Agreement, Sympathy Maxim, and Modesty Maxim were also proposed by Leech.

Tact Maxim

Tact maxim refers to minimising the cost to others while maximising the benefit to others. In this maxim, the speaker minimises the cost (and thus maximises the benefit) for the listener. Example: Could I halt or interrupt you for 3 minutes?

Generosity Maxim

The maximisation of generosity refers to minimising benefits while maximising costs to oneself. This maxim is self-centred, whereas the tact maxim is concerned with others (it focuses on the speaker and says that others should be put first instead of the self). Example: Today, you must come and have breakfast with me.

Approbation Maxim

Approbation Maxim means minimising criticism of others while maximising praise of others. This adage is used to avoid saying hurtful things about others, especially the listener. Example: We understand you are perfect in summary; could you sum up this test?

Agreement Maxim

Agreement Maxim refers to minimising the expression of disagreement between oneself and others while maximising the expression of agreement between oneself and others. In this maxim, disagreement is usually expressed as regret or partial agreement. Example: She does not want me to take the big parcel; she rather wants me to take the small one.

Sympathy Maxim

The sympathy maxim refers to minimising antipathy and maximising sympathy between oneself and others. In this case, the accomplishments of others, for example, must be recognised and evaluated. On the other hand, when tragedy strikes someone else, they must be shown sympathy or condolences. Example: I am so sorry for your mom's death. Have my condolences.

Modesty Maxim

Modesty maxim means to minimise self-praise and maximise self-criticism. Both the approbation and modesty maxims are concerned with the speaker's degree of good or bad evaluation of others or himself. However, this maxim is usually used when apologising for something. Example: Hey! I am so careless; I have my door key missing.

The Importance of Speech Acts in Language Learning The speech acts are a group of words created by the speaker to make interactional conversation and make new acts such as apology, prevention, permission, request, etc. It is crucial, as it is for reaching the intention; unless we recognise the intended meaning produced by some speech acts, we will not be able to give an opinion about the position of a speaker regarding what s/he utters and attribute the good thoughts and aims to a participant (Schiffrin, 2005). Furthermore, recognising the purposes of utterances is often essential to successful communication. However, the relationship between the linguistic structure and its implicit function must be clarified (Searle, 1975). Searle presents many parameters that differentiate his speech acts. Nevertheless, the numerous influences are the fit Direction, of which there are a couple of important ones: Speech acts that present gossip to the globe fit only in issue; they express the globe as being so-described. Speech acts produce a world-to-word fit if they propose that interlocutors behave so that the world comes to provide the description. Searle (1975:158) notes, "Direction of fit is always a consequence of an illocutionary point. Building our taxonomy fully around this distinction in the Direction of fit would be exquisite. Still, though it will compute mostly in our taxonomy, I cannot make it the fundamental basis of the prizes," Roberts, C. (2018). In this manner, Searle (1969) classified speech acts into five essential types called the taxonomy of speech acts for the illocutionary influence used to explain communication in contexts. They are as follows: Commissives, Directives, Representatives, Declarations, and Expressives: Austin (1965) and Searle (1975) have suggested the speech acts must meet particular circumstances to be successful. The cases were indicated to be felicitous ones, and they correlated to the structure and position of the point of the meeting. For instance, at a birthday ceremony, people interact for many things, such as giving gifts, kissing, and hugging him or her.. According to the classifications of Searle (1969) and Cohen (1996), speech acts can be classified into five categories: (1) Representatives (claims, assertions, reports) (2) Directives (requests, suggestions, and commands). (3) Expressives (complaints, apologies, thanks). (4) Commissives (threats, promises, and offers). (5) Declarative (decrees, declarations) This is related to how the speech acts affect the context. So as the language philosopher Searle's classifications with an explanation of the speech act are as follows:

“Representatives were defined as kinds of speech acts that include a description of a statement of a fact and

assertions connected to the truth or falsity of what the speakers probably think and believe to be the case or not. The utterances are perhaps true or false, as they hope to describe them. The pragmatics of the sentence shows the direction of the words and what the sentences or paragraphs mean. For instance, if some person states, That teacher is outstanding, No one should believe his or her speech without confirming him or her until everybody knows if it was right or wrong."

Directives are acts by which a person tries to get someone else to do something else. The utterance sender is seeking what he or she wants to send. The destination of the phrase and words uttered by the speaker has an understandable meaning for all. For example, a circumstance that happens every day is a habit, like an asker who asks anything from another to respond to it. Related verbs to the Directives include warning, inviting, requesting, daring, directing, summoning, commanding, challenging, questioning, begging, reassuring, advising, asking, bidding, ordering, forbidding, instructing, suggesting, defying, and entreating.

"Commissives: are a type of speech act used by the speaker for doing anything and the sides of the used sentence. Commitment is the same as the destination of explaining the intention through words and expressing what is inside the speaker. Some related words to the Commissives: vowing, intending, pledging, and promising to do what is needed and what was asked to be done."(Takkula et al. 2008).

Expressive speech is used to explain a psychological situation and express its fluent mood. When any person says "forgive me," it refers to something wrong that is unusual and unacceptable socially. Some related verbs to the expressive are: Thanking, greeting, congratulating, regretting, condoling, surprising, blaming, and welcoming.

Declarations are speech acts that change according to the content of the words in a sentence. The speakers perform the actions by stating their status. The linguist Hatch (1992) mentioned that declarations are speech acts that include speech and what the speakers want to say and perform. Some related verbs to the Declarations: Appointing, declaring, dismissing, resigning, and firing from employment, naming, blessing, and sentencing.

Conclusion

The literature review and the theoretical framework in this study involve some fundamental definitions that facilitate the comprehension of speech acts regarding the politeness maxim. The purpose of the study is to examine the awareness of Arab-Libyan and Amazigh-Libyan EFL learners regarding the speech acts of politeness maxim. In various social contexts. 2. to investigate the politeness realisation of the participants while producing the speech acts of permission, request, apology, question, opinion, and suggestion. 3. To investigate the similarities and differences between Arab-Libyan and Amazigh-Libyan EFL(non-Arab minority in Libya) users responding to speech-act patterns. In a nutshell, the Politeness maxim has a role in the investigation because it is used by people in their social interactions and specific contexts, such as knowing what to say, how to say it, when to say it, and how to interact with others. Being polite is very important to creating good communication between oneself and others. This means that both the speaker and the hearer should exercise caution when using language in communication, and this caution refers to the politeness maxim.

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